

Technical Appendix

Derivation of Equation (4)

We present a clear formulation of the Owen approximation of Shapley values within a hierarchical coalition structure, as this specific approach appears to be absent from existing published literature. To ease our formulation, we start from a simple extension of the Shapley formula:

$$\varphi_i(Q, \mathcal{N}) = \sum_{S \subseteq \mathcal{N} \setminus \{i\}} \frac{1}{n \cdot \binom{n-1}{|S|}} \Delta_i(Q \cup S) \quad (8)$$

where n is the cardinality of \mathcal{N} . Eq. (8) assigns a unique distribution of the total worth $\nu(\mathcal{N})$ generated by cooperation among players in a coalition game, and is extended by assuming that all coalitions S are supported by a persistent set of players Q . The regular Shapley value (Shapley 1953, Eq.12) are obtained from (8) as $\varphi_i(\emptyset, \mathcal{N})$. The persistent set Q is used for the Owen approximation.

The Owen coalition value (Owen 1977) is an extension of the Shapley value, and it is a quantity $\Omega_i(\mathcal{T})$ that represents the worth of player i in a game with coalition structure \mathcal{T} . The original formulation for a two-level coalition structure hierarchy³ works as follows. Consider a player i belonging to team $T_j \in \mathcal{T} \downarrow$. Then

$$\Omega_i(\mathcal{T}) = \sum_{\substack{H \subseteq M \\ j \notin H}} \sum_{\substack{S \subset T_j \\ i \notin S}} \frac{1}{m \cdot \binom{m-1}{|H|}} \cdot \frac{1}{t_j \cdot \binom{t_j-1}{|S|}} \Delta_i(Q_H \cup S) \quad (9)$$

where $M = \{1 \dots m\}$ is the set of structured coalition indices of \mathcal{T} , $Q_H = \bigcup_{k \in H} T_k$, and $t_j = |T_j|$.

Eq. (9) can be seen as a two-level Shapley value, where inside a team T_j all coalitions are possible, but once a coalition $S \subset T_j$ is formed, only a restricted *all-or-nothing* form of cooperation with the other teams is possible. It is possible to rewrite (9) by explicitly identifying the Shapley value for the subsets S of T_j . By doing so with (8) and applying simple algebraic transformations, we get

$$\Omega_i(\mathcal{T}) = \sum_{H \subseteq M \setminus \{j\}} \frac{1}{m \cdot \binom{m-1}{|H|}} \varphi_i(Q_H, T_j) \quad (10)$$

i.e. the Owen coalition value is defined on the basis of the Shapley value (extended as in Eq. (8)), similarly to the approach of the so-called “two-steps value” formulation of (Owen 2013, p.300).

Example 3. Consider a coalition structure $\mathcal{T} = \{\{1, 2\}, \{3, 4, 5\}, \{6\}\}$. The coalition value $\Omega_1(\mathcal{T}) =$

³In a two-level coalition structure hierarchy \mathcal{T} , we have $\mathcal{T} \downarrow = \{T_1 \dots T_m\}$, and $\forall 1 \leq i \leq m: T_i \downarrow = \perp$.

$\eta_1(\emptyset, \mathcal{T})$ is the weighted sums of eight marginals:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \frac{1}{6} \Delta_1(\emptyset) & \frac{1}{6} \Delta_1(\{2\}) \\ \frac{1}{6} \Delta_1(\{3, 4, 5, 6\}) & \frac{1}{6} \Delta_1(\{3, 4, 5, 6, 2\}) \\ \frac{1}{12} \Delta_1(\{6\}) & \frac{1}{12} \Delta_1(\{6, 2\}) \\ \frac{1}{12} \Delta_1(\{3, 4, 5\}) & \frac{1}{12} \Delta_1(\{3, 4, 5, 2\}) \end{array}$$

Since player 1 is in an a-priori coalition with player 2, the other two teams $\{3, 4, 5\}$ and $\{6\}$ can only appear as a whole. As a consequence, the Owen approximation of the Shapley coefficients only observes some coalitions, that preserve the integrity of the teams that are in a separate branch of the tree hierarchy.

Observe that $\Omega_i(\mathcal{T}) \neq \varphi_i(\emptyset, \mathcal{N})$, as only a selected structured subsets of coalitions are formed (see (López and Saboya 2009) for an in-depth analysis of this relation).

The two-level formulation is easily extended to an arbitrary hierarchy of coalitions, and this idea has been pioneered for image data by the SHAP Partition Explainer (Lundberg 2020; Shrikumar, Greenside, and Kundaje 2017; Lundberg and Lee 2017). Therefore a hierarchical *Owen coalition value* can be obtained rewriting Eq. (10) on top of other Owen coalition values for a coalition T , as long as T is not an indivisible coalition. The concept is also briefly sketched in (Owen 1977, p.87), but we rewrite the equation to have a simple recursive formula that is general for m -ary and binary hierarchical coalition structures, as in Eqs. (2) and (3), respectively.

Binary and multi-way tree hierarchies (i.e. $m > 2$). Consider Eq. (10) and replace the summation over the subsets of indices M with a uniform *subset U of the sub-coalition structure of $T \downarrow$* , making the marginal contribution of Eq. (1) as the base case of the recursion, and adding a persistent set Q as done for Eq. (8).

$$\Omega_i(Q, T) = \begin{cases} \sum_{U \subseteq T \downarrow \setminus \{T_j\}} \frac{1}{m \cdot \binom{m-1}{|U|}} \Omega_i(Q \cup Q_U, T_j) & \text{if } T \downarrow = \{T_1 \dots T_m\} \\ \frac{1}{|T|} \Delta_T(Q) & \text{if } T \text{ is indivisible} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $Q_U = \bigcup_{k=1}^{|U|} U_k$, and assuming T_j contains i . As before, indivisible coalitions receive uniform attributions among all players. The Owen coalition value for player i using Eq. (11) is obtained from $\Omega_i(\emptyset, \mathcal{T})$, with \mathcal{T} the HCS root. When $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{N}\}$, $\mathcal{T} \downarrow = \perp$, then Eq. (11) reduces to $\varphi_i(Q, \mathcal{N})$, which is trivially equivalent to Eq. (8). Using a two-level HCS, then Eq. (11) is equivalent to Eq. (9) and Eq. (10). For arbitrary nested hierarchies, the equation expands, generating the coalitions Q that may pair with the set T containing player i , following the hierarchy constraints.

Example 4. Consider a three-level HCS

$$\mathcal{T} = \left\{ \left\{ \{1, 2\}, \{3, 4\} \right\}, \left\{ \{5, 6\}, \{7\}, \{8\} \right\} \right\}$$

The hierarchical coalition value $\Omega_1(\emptyset, \mathcal{T})$ is the weighted sums of eight marginals:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\emptyset) & \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{2\}) \\ \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{5, 6, 7, 8\}) & \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{5, 6, 7, 8, 2\}) \\ \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{3, 4\}) & \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{3, 4, 2\}) \\ \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{5, 6, 7, 8, 3, 4\}) & \frac{1}{8}\Delta_1(\{5, 6, 7, 8, 3, 4, 2\}) \end{array}$$

Coalitions can pair with player 1 following the hierarchy. Therefore $\{3, 4\}$ and $\{5, 6, 7, 8\}$ can only appear as a whole block from the point-of-view of player 1, even if the partition $\{5, 6, 7, 8\}$ is not a single coalition.

Eq. (11) applies to m -ary coalition structure, but the case for binary hierarchies is simpler. By assuming $m = 2$, the formula $\Omega_i(Q, T)$ of Eq. (11) can be simplified, obtaining Eq. (4) and completing our derivation.

Proof of Theorem 1

Applying Eq. (4) to a partition T that admits a sub-coalition structure $T \downarrow = \{T_1, T_2\}$ creates four branches (two for $i \in T_1$ and two for $i \in T_2$) and necessitates two ν evaluations. Since we are assuming the BHCS hierarchy to be a balanced tree with depth d , we can define the total number $a(d)$ of ν evaluations for the expansion of all nodes up to depth d . Such quantity $a(d)$ follows a linear recurrence sequence represented by Eq. (12)

$$a(d) = \begin{cases} 4 \cdot a(d-1) + 2 & \text{if } d > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } d = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Recursion from Eq. (12) can be eliminated, since the equation is a well-known non-homogeneous linear recurrence with constant coefficients, having solution

$$a(d) = \alpha \cdot a(d-1) + \beta = \frac{\beta(\alpha^{d-1} - 1)}{\alpha - 1}$$

By using $\alpha = 4$ and $\beta = 2$, Eq. (12) simplifies to

$$a(d) = \frac{2}{3}(4^{d-1} - 1) \approx O(4^d) \quad (13)$$

i.e., the time complexity of Eq. (4) exhibits exponential growth.

Pseudo-code of the Owen approximation algorithm

A limitation of equation Eq. (4) is that the same coalitions are generated in the recursive expansion of $\Omega_i(\emptyset, \mathcal{T})$, for different players $i \in \mathcal{N}$. This issue may severely limit the performance, but it can be easily solved either by memoization, or by generating all the coalitions using a tree visit. An efficient iterative implementation of the latter is sketched in Algorithm 1, and it is conceptually equivalent to the Partition Explainer of SHAP (Lundberg 2020). Therefore it does not constitute a novel paper contribution, but we report it for reader's convenience and self-containment.

Algorithm 1: Iterative implementation of Eq. (4).

```

1 function OwenValues( $\nu, \mathcal{T}, b$ )
2   foreach  $i \in \mathcal{N}$  do  $\Omega[i] \leftarrow 0$ 
3    $queue.push(\langle 1, \emptyset, \mathcal{T}, \nu(\emptyset), \nu(\mathcal{N}) \rangle)$ 
4   while  $queue$  is not empty do
5      $w, Q, T, v_Q, v_{Q \cup T} \leftarrow queue.pop()$ 
6     if  $T$  is indivisible or  $b \leq 1$  then
7       foreach  $i \in T$  do
8          $\Omega[i] \leftarrow \Omega[i] + \frac{w}{|T|}(v_{Q \cup T} - v_Q)$ 
9     else
10       $T_1, T_2 \leftarrow T \downarrow$ 
11       $v_{Q \cup T_1} \leftarrow \nu(Q \cup T_1)$ 
12       $v_{Q \cup T_2} \leftarrow \nu(Q \cup T_2)$ 
13       $b \leftarrow b - 2$ 
14       $queue.push(\langle \frac{w}{2}, Q, T_1, v_Q, v_{Q \cup T_1} \rangle,$ 
15                 $\langle \frac{w}{2}, Q \cup T_2, T_1, v_{Q \cup T_2}, v_{Q \cup T} \rangle,$ 
16                 $\langle \frac{w}{2}, Q, T_2, v_Q, v_{Q \cup T_2} \rangle,$ 
17                 $\langle \frac{w}{2}, Q \cup T_1, T_2, v_{Q \cup T_1}, v_{Q \cup T} \rangle)$ 
18   return  $\Omega$ 

```

Algorithm 1 operates at the partition level. It starts from the full coalition at the root \mathcal{T} of the BPT hierarchy (measuring the difference $\nu(\mathcal{N}) - \nu(\emptyset)$). Partitions are inserted into a queue, assumed to be ordered by a priority w . It then proceeds by splitting the next partition with the highest w , using Eq. (4). Each split requires two model evaluations (line 13), thus reducing the budget b by 2. The splitting continues until the budget b is consumed, or all partitions left are indivisible.

Pseudo-code of the BPT algorithm

Detailed pseudo-code for the BPT algorithm can be found in (Salembier and Garrido 2000; Randrianasoa et al. 2018, 2021), but a pseudo-code is provided in Algorithm 2. It uses three functions:

- **init_bpt**: initializes the unitary partitions i of the BPT hierarchy from the individual pixels px of the input image x , and creates the heap of all the pairs of adjacent pixels.
- **get_dist**: computes the distance between two (adjacent) partitions i and j using Eq. (5).
- **build_bpt**: iteratively merges adjacent partitions in *distance-order*, each time creating a new merged partition k , and updates the weights in the heap accordingly. The function proceeds as long as there are adjacent partitions, i.e. it stops when all pixels are merged into a single root partition.

Once Algorithm 2 has generated a *merging sequence*, it can be efficiently stored into 6 arrays:

- $leaf_idx[i]$: the image pixel of unitary coalition i , with $i \in [1, n]$;
- $left_branch[k]$ and $right_branch[k]$: the two partition

indexes resulting from the split $T_{k\downarrow}$ of each non-unitary coalition k , with $k \in [n + 1, 2n - 1]$;

- $start[k]$ and $end[k]$: index interval of pixels for the non-unitary partition k ;
- $pixels$: the sorted array of pixel indexes, indexed by $start$ and end .

Therefore, the memory requirement for the BPT hierarchy is $\Theta(6n)$ integers.

The core data structure is a graph of the partitions (nodes), paired with the list of adjacencies (edges). The adjacency list needs to be sorted efficiently in order to extract the edge $adj = (i, j)$ having the smallest $dist(i, j)$, as defined by Eq. (5) and computed by function `get_dist`. To do so, a heap data structure is a reasonable choice. Merging coalitions therefore requires to both modify the nodes and update the edges. This process, described at line 16 of `build_bpt` and depicted in Figure 2/B, shows that each merge operation requires to traverse the adjacency list of the merged partitions. Further details can be found in (Randrianasoa et al. 2018).

Python implementation

ShapBPT is implemented in Python. A snippet of the python code using the *ShapBPT* package to obtain a Shapley explanation for a given image using the masking function ν is provided in Algorithm 3. While not detailed in the paper, the implementation supports multi-class explanations, similarly to (Lundberg 2020).

Sensitivity of the distance function

We run a small sensitivity analysis of the distance function $dist(T_i, T_j)$ over 100 randomly sampled images from ImageNet-S₅₀. Unless otherwise stated, all experiments use the same *ResNet-50* classifier, a fixed evaluation budget b of 100 model calls per image and the ShapBPT hyperparameters reported in the main text.

We consider three variations of the distance function.

- *Default* (Eq. (5)) - color \times area $\times \sqrt{\text{perimeter}}$.
- *No-perimeter* - color \times area (drops the perimeter term).
- *No-color* - area $\times \sqrt{\text{perimeter}}$ (drops the color term).

Area cannot be dropped, as it generates imbalanced trees. We report the *relative change* ($\Delta\%$) in *AU-IoU* and *max-IoU* against the default distance.

Distance variant	$\Delta AU-IoU \uparrow$	$\Delta max-IoU \downarrow$
Default (Eq. (5))	0.0%	0.0%
No-perimeter term	-2.65%	-3.78%
No-color term	-12.61%	-24.40%

Dropping the perimeter term produces a small loss in *AU-IoU* of -2.65% and a small loss in *max-IoU* of -3.78%, showing that the presence of the perimeter term provides a benefit. Dropping the color term results in significant losses (-12.61% in *AU-IoU* and -24.40% in *max-IoU*), which shows that color term is very relevant. Therefore, the default color-area-perimeter distance of

Eq. (5) is a well-behaved compromise: inexpensive to compute and close to the Pareto front.

We plan to study more complex alternatives in a future work.

Algorithm 2: Pseudo-code of the BPT algorithm.

```
1 function init_bpt( $\mathcal{X}$ :image)
2   foreach pixel  $px$  of image  $x$  do
3      $i \leftarrow$  make_partition()
4      $minR[i] \leftarrow maxR[i] \leftarrow R[px]$ 
5      $minG[i] \leftarrow maxG[i] \leftarrow G[px]$ 
6      $minB[i] \leftarrow maxB[i] \leftarrow B[px]$ 
7      $area[i] \leftarrow 1$ ;  $perimeter[i] \leftarrow 4$ ;  $root[i] \leftarrow i$ 
8   foreach pair of partitions  $i, j$  that have adjacent pixels
   in  $x$  do
9     heap_push( $heap$ , make_adjacency( $i, j$ ,
   weight=get_dist( $i, j$ )))

1 function get_dist( $i, j$ )
2    $rangeR \leftarrow \max(maxR[i] - maxR[j] -$ 
    $\min(minR[i] - minR[j])$ 
3    $rangeG \leftarrow \max(maxG[i] - maxG[j] -$ 
    $\min(minG[i] - minG[j])$ 
4    $rangeB \leftarrow \max(maxB[i] - maxB[j] -$ 
    $\min(minB[i] - minB[j])$ 
5    $area \leftarrow area[i] + area[j]$ 
6    $perimeter \leftarrow perimeter[i] + perimeter[j] -$ 
    $2 * adjacent\_perimeter[i, j]$ 
7    $color\_score \leftarrow (rangeR^2 + rangeG^2 + rangeB^2)$ 
8   return  $color\_score * area * \sqrt{perimeter}$ 

1 function build_bpt()
2   while  $heap$  is not empty do
3      $adj \leftarrow$  heap_pop( $heap$ )
4      $i, j \leftarrow$  partitions in  $adj$ 
5      $k \leftarrow$  make_partition()
6      $minR[k] \leftarrow \min(minR[i], minR[j])$ 
7      $maxR[k] \leftarrow \max(maxR[i], maxR[j])$ 
8      $minG[k] \leftarrow \min(minG[i], minG[j])$ 
9      $maxG[k] \leftarrow \max(maxG[i], maxG[j])$ 
10     $minB[k] \leftarrow \min(minB[i], minB[j])$ 
11     $maxB[k] \leftarrow \max(maxB[i], maxB[j])$ 
12     $area[k] \leftarrow area[i] + area[j]$ 
13     $perimeter[k] \leftarrow perimeter[i] + perimeter[j]$ 
14     $root[k] \leftarrow k$ ;  $root[i] \leftarrow root[j] \leftarrow k$ 
15     $left\_branch[k] \leftarrow i$ ;  $right\_branch[k] \leftarrow j$ 
16    merge linked lists of adjacencies of  $i$  and  $j$  into a
    single linked list for partition  $k$ , updating the heap
    weights using get_dist since partitions  $i$  and  $j$  are
    now merged together.
```

Algorithm 3: Example Python code.

```
1 from shap_bpt import Explainer
2  $explainer = Explainer(v, image\_to\_explain,$ 
    $num\_explained\_classes)$ 
3  $shap\_values = explainer.explain\_instance(max\_evals=b)$ 
```

Evaluation details

Experiment E1

This experiment employs the *1K-V2* pretrained model (Vryniotis 2021), utilizing the ResNet50 architecture (He et al. 2016) available in the PyTorch library, which reports an accuracy of 80.858%. Masking is applied by substituting affected pixels with a uniform gray color. The analysis is conducted on the ImageNet-S₅₀ dataset (Gao et al. 2022), which provides precise ground-truth masks for a selected subset of images. To maintain consistency, only images for which the ground-truth mask corresponds to the top predicted class are considered, resulting in a total of 574 images.

Figure 6 shows additional saliency maps for the **E1** experiment, generated by explaining the classification of the ResNet50 model on the samples from the ImageNet-S₅₀ dataset.

Figure 7 reports the results for **E1**, with one table for each of the four scores, plus one for the evaluation time (logscale). All reported times were computed with an Intel Core i9 CPU, an Nvidia 4070 GPU, and 16GB of RAM. Scores are drawn as boxplots (treating values outside 10 times the interquartile range as outliers, drawn as fuchsia dots), with a method symbol on the right (see the legend for the mapping).

In **E1**, BPT is positioned close or at the top of every score. In this case, AA has a slightly better AUC^+ score, but a worse AUC^- score than BPT. The BPT method seems to be particularly effective at the IoU scores $max-IoU$ and $AU-IoU$, which can be explained by its capacity of recognizing the borders of the objects, by following a data-aware hierarchy. Only GradCAM reaches similar IoU scores, but in practice the localization of GradCAM is more blurred and fuzzy (this limitation is apparently not well captured by the two IoU scores).

Experiment E2

One important limitation of experiments relying on some unknown black-box model is that the ground truth may not be faithful, as the model may classify an object based on partial details or using weak correlations. To overcome this limitation, experiment **E2** replicates **E1** adopting an ideal model which perfectly follows the ground truth.

The ideal model

$$\nu_{\text{lin}}(S) = \frac{|S \cap G|}{|G|}$$

is a linear function that outputs the proportion of pixels of S that belong to the ground truth G . Since ν_{lin} is not a neural network, CAM methods cannot be used and are excluded. By using a linear model, the experimental environment has minimal noise, is therefore simpler to interpret, and provides a better baseline for assessment, even if it is less realistic than a deep learning model.

Figure 8 shows the results of experiment **E2**, while a subset of the generated saliency maps are depicted in Figure 9. The results shows the effectiveness of the BPT explanation strategy: all BPT- b achieve better scores than their AA- b counterpart, for the same budget b .

Experiment E3

Experiment **E3** replicates the setup of **E1** and **E2**, but employs a Vision Transformer model, specifically *SwinViT* (Liu et al. 2021). Vision Transformer models are known for their robustness against partial occlusion of recognized objects, making it more challenging for model-agnostic methods to analyze their behavior by selectively masking parts of the image. A summary of the results is presented in Figure 11, while a selection of saliency maps from the same set of examples is depicted in Figure 10.

Due to the limitations of the LRP method’s implementation, which does not support this transformer-based architecture, we excluded it from the results. Analyzing the explanations produced by different methods, it is evident that all approaches, except for BPT, generate significantly more ambiguous saliency maps, attributing considerable importance to background features while failing to focus adequately on the classified objects. In contrast, the maps produced by BPT appear clearer and more focused. Notably, BPT consistently achieves superior performance across all evaluation metrics.

This experiment provides valuable insights, as Vision Transformer models exhibit increased robustness to input masking, making them particularly challenging to interpret using model-agnostic methods. Unlike convolutional models, these transformers-based model require clever feature replacement techniques for behavior probing, and ShapBPT seems to be significantly better than the other methods.

Figure 6: Additional saliency maps generated for the **E1** experiment.

Figure 7: Results for four metrics across 574 images from the ImageNet-S₅₀ dataset, with methods ranked by performance (highest at the top) for experiment E1. Arrows denote whether higher or lower scores are better.

Figure 8: Results for the four metrics across 574 images from the ImageNet-S₅₀ dataset, with methods ranked by performance (highest at the top) for the experiments E2.

Figure 9: Saliency maps obtained from the ideal linear model ν_{in} , experiment E2.

Figure 10: Saliency maps from selected instances in the **E3** experiment (with SwinViT).

Figure 11: Results for the four metrics across 621 images from the ImageNet-S₅₀ dataset, with methods ranked by performance (highest at the top) for the experiments **E3**.

Experiment E4

This experiment focuses on the MS-COCO dataset (Lin et al. 2014), which includes 80 object classes with diverse image sizes and aspect ratios, and a wider range of details than ImageNet. The task is object detection, evaluated on 5,000 images (from the validation set) with bounding box and segmentation map annotations. A pre-trained Yolo11s model (Jocher and Qiu 2024) from the Ultralytics library (319 layers, 9.4M parameters, 21.7 GFLOPs) is used as a black-box model for its accuracy and fast inference. The XCV task involves highlighting detected objects and comparing them to segmentation maps, with evaluation based on performance curve metrics and ground-truth comparisons, as explained in Experimental Assessment Section.

Also in this case, ShapBPT demonstrates strong capability in highlighting the boundaries of detected objects, outperforming AA in most metrics.

Experiments E5

This experiment considers a multiclass regression model rather than a classification model. The objective is to determine the presence (positive prediction) or absence (negative prediction) of specific facial features, such as brown hair or eyeglasses. The explainable AI task involves identifying the regions that contribute to these predictions. A score $\nu(\mathcal{N}) > \nu(\emptyset)$ indicates the presence of the feature, while a score $\nu(\mathcal{N}) < \nu(\emptyset)$ signifies its absence.

The dataset used for this study is CelebA-HQ (Karras et al. 2018), which includes 40 facial attributes. For this analysis, we focus on two attributes—brown hair and eyeglasses—for which ground-truth segmentation masks are available. A total of 106 images were evaluated. The model employed is a pre-trained sequential convolutional neural network (CNN) provided by (Batra 2020).

An example of the XCV task is illustrated in Figure 14, where multiple instances are analyzed. The first three are:

- 0.1 A subject with brown hair, correctly identified as having brown hair (positive score).
- 0.2 A subject with black hair, correctly identified as not having brown hair (negative score).
- 0.3 A subject wearing eyeglasses, correctly identified as having them (positive score).

For positive cases (a, c, d, and e), the Shapley values are positive in the regions contributing to the positive prediction. Conversely, for negative cases (b and f), the Shapley values are negative in the areas responsible for the negative prediction. Since CAM methods do not inherently satisfy the efficiency axiom of Shapley values, their outputs are considered in absolute terms.

Results of the evaluation are reported in the tables in Figure 15. This experiment shows again the capacity of BPT-based methods to adaptively follow the borders of the activating regions, achieving high performances particularly on IoU scores. Note that also in this case, as previously discussed for **E1**, the ground truth can only be considered as a weak approximation of the model’s learnt representation,

as the model is likely to use multiple features of the subject face to determine the presence or the absence of a specific attribute, not just the shape of the hair or the eyeglasses. Nonetheless, the localization of that area remains more precise when data-awareness is used.

Figure 12: Examples of the **E4** experiment, using the MS-COCO dataset.

Figure 13: Results for the 274 test images from MS-COCO, with methods ranked by performance, for the experiments **E4**.

Figure 14: Examples of the **E5** experiment, explaining facial attributes using the CelebA dataset.

Figure 15: Results for the four metrics for the **E5** experiment on the CelebA dataset on 400 images.

Experiments E6

Experiment **E6** considers the problem of explaining anomalies detected by an Anomaly Detection (AD) system on image data. This experiment is based on the work of (Ravi et al. 2021) where anomalies in images are detected using a Variational AutoEncoder-Generative Adversarial Network (VAE-GAN) model by means of anomaly localization. We use the MVTEC benchmark dataset (Bergmann et al. 2019) which has 5000 high quality images with defective and non-defective samples from 15 different categories of objects. We selected the *hazelnut* object category from the dataset.

Figure 16: Workflow of the explainable AI applied to the Anomaly Detection system of **E6**.

The pipeline of this system is depicted in Figure 16. An input image x is reconstructed into x' using a one-class VAE-GAN classifier. The anomaly map am captures the reconstruction error, which sums up both the potential anomalies of x as well as the noise. An XAI method can be employed to separate the noise from the detected anomalies, thus localizing if and where the anomalies are present. In this context, the function $\nu(S)$ is a MSE loss on the anomaly map am itself. Since $\nu(S)$ is a MSE loss and not a neural network, CAM methods cannot be used. Therefore, we generate saliency maps using BPT, AA and LIME. We use values 100, 500, and 1000 for the budget value b . For LIME, we use 100, 500 and 1000 a-priori segments, respectively.

As the MVTEC dataset has proper ground truth masks for the expected anomalous regions, we can compute all the four scores defined in the Experimental Assessment Section. Figure 17 shows the AD problem on three input images. For each input, a row shows: the input x , its reconstruction x' through the VAE-GAN model, the anomaly map am , the explanation generated by BPT with $b=500$, by AA with $b=500$ and by LIME with $b=500$ and 100 segments. The true intersection-over-union is also shown, highlighting the true positives (TP), the false positives (FP) and the false negatives (FN). The ground truth G is also shown, for reference.

Results are reported in Figure 18. Again, all three XCV methods are capable of identifying the anomalous regions on the various samples, but BPT significantly outperforms the others. This is particularly true for the task of identifying the exact region, which is highlighted by the very high *max-IoU*

scores.

Experiments E7

Similar to E1 using the ViT-Base 16 model (Dosovitskiy et al. 2020). Saliency maps are illustrated in Figure 19. Results are reported in Figure 20. Similarly to E3 we observe a tendency of BPT to show more focused explanations than AA, and BPT achieves significantly better automated scores than AA.

Figure 17: Selected examples in the Anomaly Detection system for experiment E6.

Figure 18: Results for the 4 metrics for the experiments E6 on 280 images.

Figure 19: Saliency maps from selected instances in the E7 experiment (with ViT-Base 16).

Figure 20: Results for the 4 metrics for the experiments E7 on 593 images.

ANOVA results

To assess statistical significance, we conducted one-way ANOVA tests for each of the four scores (AUC^+ , AUC^- , $AU-IoU$ and $max-IoU$) obtained by competing explainers across the full test split. Scores are computed per image (one sample per image \times explainer). We assume that independence is guaranteed since each image is a different problem. We test the null hypothesis (H_0) of equal means across all sample populations. A p -value threshold of 0.05 was used to determine significance, and H_0 is rejected when $p < 0.05$. In all cases, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that the results are statistically significant. Table 2 reports the results of the one-way ANOVA tests.

E8 - User Preference Study

The study was conceived to quantify *perceived intuitiveness and usefulness* of four explanation techniques: **AA-1000**, **BPT-1000**, **LIME-1000** and **GradCAM**, when applied to vision classification tasks of varying semantic granularity. Because subjective preference is hard to measure on an absolute scale, we employed a *within-subject, forced-ranking* design: each participant was shown four explanations side-by-side for a given image-classification task and asked to order them from most to least helpful. Saliency maps were permuted across tasks to mitigate position and label biases, while keeping the identity of each method hidden to every participant. This design yields ordinal data that permit robust, non-parametric comparisons without assuming interval-scale judgments.

Figure 21: Sample structure of the questionnaire given to the 20 human subjects.

Experimental setting. Twenty volunteers (S1-S20) recruited from graduate students completed four ranking trials corresponding to the “Butterfly”, “Ladybug”, “Street-Sign”, and “Bench” images. Recruited students have technical background in Machine Learning, but not in-depth knowledge of explainability and its associated methods. Each trial presented the raw image and four colour-coded saliency maps produced by the hidden methods. Participants gave a total of $20 \times 4 = 80$ rank vectors and thus 80 independent judgments for every method (see a sample in Fig-

ure 21). After the ranking stage, subjects confirmed they understood the task.

Rankings distribution of XCV methods by 20 users

Figure 22: Distribution of the rankings across the four methods given by the 20 user subjects.

Results and discussion. Figure 22 summarises the outcome. BPT dominates the leftmost cluster, being selected first in $41/80 = 51\%$ of the trials and never relegated to fourth more than 7 times; its mean rank is $\bar{r}_{\text{BPT}} = 1.79$. GradCAM follows with a respectable first-place share (33%) and $\bar{r} = 2.41$; LIME is more evenly spread across the second and third positions ($\bar{r} = 2.56$), while AA is strongly skewed to the bottom (38/80 fourth-place votes, $\bar{r} = 3.24$).

A Friedman test ($\chi^2_{(k=3)} = 19.56$, $p = 0.0002 < 0.05$, H_0 rejected) confirms that at least one explanation technique is ranked differently from the others with very high statistical confidence. To determine the significance, we follow with a Nemenyi pairwise comparison and identify BPT-vs-GradCAM and BPT-vs-LIME as marginally significant ($p = 0.079$ and $p = 0.092$, marginal at $p < \alpha = 0.10$), and BPT-vs-AA as strongly significant ($p = 0.000081$). Taken together, the data argue that human users consistently find BPT explanations clearer and more intuitive, supporting its adoption as the default interpretability method in similar visual-classification pipelines. Further discussions with the subject confirms the preference due to the clear and crisp presentation, with little noise and not blurred. While results are statistically significant, we acknowledge that this user study is small and preliminary, and we will make a larger study as a future work.

Limitations of SAM for Owen-style Shapley attribution.

The *Segment Anything Model* (SAM) provides, via its *SamAutomaticMaskGenerator*, a flat set of object-proposal masks that are pruned only by *box-level* non-maximum suppression, leaving many pixel overlaps and no parent-child ordering among the masks. As a result, the masks neither partition the image domain nor form a nested hierarchy (Kirillov et al. 2023). These properties violate the disjoint-coalition and containment assumptions required by

Experiment	No. of Methods	No. of Images	AUC^+	AUC^-	$max-IoU$	$AU-IoU$
E1	14	574	0.0	4.10e-197	0.0	2.49e-135
E2	12	574	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
E3	14	621	0.0	4.56e-248	0.0	0.0
E4	9	274	1.09e-111	1.54e-15	1.94e-96	1.29e-18
E5	14	436	0.0	0.0	1.36e-31	1.64e-13
E6	9	280	2.12e-145	4.03e-175	8.53e-260	0.009
E7	13	593	0.0	1.27e-209	6.06e-162	0.0

Table 2: One-way ANOVA summary of all four metrics across the seven experiments.

the Owen extension of Shapley values, whose recursive additivity hinges on a binary partition tree (BPT). Consequently, raw SAM outputs cannot be plugged directly into hierarchical-Shapley frameworks without additional structure.

One direction is the *Explain Any Concept* (EAC), which couples SAM with Shapley values to attribute predictions to a *flat* set of SAM-derived concept masks (Sun et al. 2023). Because these masks may overlap and are treated independently, the Shapley computation is executed *once* on the initial segmentation, with no mechanism for iterative refinement of coalitions. This design means EAC’s faithfulness is entirely dependent on the initial SAM proposals already capturing all semantically relevant regions (like LIME), thereby breaking requirement R2 of the ShapBPT framework (i.e. progressive, data-driven refinement of the coalition hierarchy). In scenarios where the first-pass segmentation misses fine-grained or contextually important regions, EAC cannot recover them, whereas ShapBPT’s recursive splits can adaptively hone in on such details.

A viable research direction toward a SAM-based Hierarchical Coalition Structure (HCS) is to post-process the SAM mask set into a non-overlapping, nested hierarchy that is compatible with the Owen recursion. One potential starting point follows the *Panoptic-SAM* pipeline⁴, which “paints” SAM masks from largest to smallest to obtain a panoptic segmentation; a region-adjacency graph could then be constructed and merged iteratively (e.g., by similarity or containment) to yield a balanced tree. Still the tree is not strictly binary, which either needs a binarization or requires a reformulation of (4) to deal with n -ary trees.

We plan as a future work to define a SAM-HCS and test its effectiveness against a morphology-driven BPTs, to understand how effective it is w.r.t. a fully refinable BPT structure.

Remarks on h-Shap

We considered including *h-Shap* (Teneggi, Luster, and Sulam 2022), which has a faster convergence compared to Theorem 1. However, since the object recognition task addressed by *h-Shap* is incomparable to that of the other XCV methods, as *h-Shap* treats binary-valued games only, we chose to exclude it. Despite this, we believe that *h-Shap* would also benefit from the use of BPT partitions.

⁴Panoptic Segment Anything. <https://github.com/segments-ai/panoptic-segment-anything>